

From Neighbours to Nature Stewards

How social learning in Farmer Clusters Strengthens Biodiversity Action

Policy Recommendations

- **Embed facilitation in AES design:** Require and fund trained facilitators as part of landscape-scale AES initiatives.
- **Support peer learning structures:** Encourage national CAP strategic plans to include budgets for farmer-led field days, cross-visits, and participatory monitoring.
- **Invest in facilitator training and networks:** Build EU-level training programs for facilitators to share methods, challenges, and innovations.
- **Encourage locally adapted implementation:** Avoid rigid EU-wide prescriptions; instead, allow Member States to tailor FC-like models to local socio-cultural conditions.
- **Measure identity and learning outcomes:** Develop indicators to track changes in farmer identity and social capital alongside environmental outcomes.

Introduction

Biodiversity in European farmland is in decline, threatening both agroecosystem services and long-term food system resilience. While EU agri-environmental schemes (AES) aim to reverse this trend, uptake and impact vary widely. Traditional top-down AES often fail to connect with farmers' local realities, values, and identity. In contrast, the Farmer Cluster (FC) approach offers a promising model: farmers organize locally, supported by a trained facilitator, to implement biodiversity-sensitive practices at the landscape scale.

This policy brief draws on in-depth qualitative research conducted across six European regions. Through longitudinal interviews with cluster participants, we explore how participation in FCs influences farmers' identity, values, and behaviour. The evidence shows that FCs create spaces for mutual learning and trust-building. Farmers increasingly describe themselves not just as producers, but as land stewards and educators, roles previously marginal in their self-concept. These new self-understandings increase their engagement with biodiversity goals.

The EU's environmental ambitions, particularly under the Green Deal and the future CAP, require not only technical solutions but social transformations. Supporting FC-style facilitation and embedding social learning principles in policy design is a cost-effective and politically feasible strategy to shift farmer behaviour from the ground up.

Approach and results

This policy brief is based on qualitative findings from the FRAMEwork project (2020–2025), which implemented and studied Farmer Clusters in six regions: Austria (Burgenland, Mostviertel), Czech Republic, Netherlands, and the UK (Scotland – Buchan, England – Cranborne Chase). Data include over

60 in-depth interviews conducted in years 1 and 4 of the project with farmers participating in clusters. The analysis traced changes in values, identity, and biodiversity-related practices.

- **Facilitated clusters create space for identity transformation**
At the outset, many farmers described themselves as primarily business operators or technical experts. Participation in clusters catalyzed a shift toward broader roles, including environmental stewards, community leaders, and educators. Farmers began to see biodiversity measures not as regulatory burdens but as expressions of good farming.
- **Peer exchange builds trust and motivation**
Farmers repeatedly emphasized the value of learning from each other. Facilitated meetings, field days, and shared monitoring experiences fostered mutual respect and curiosity. In the Austrian and Czech clusters, farmers began adapting practices after seeing successful examples from peers. This diffusion of innovation was more persuasive than external expert advice.
- **Facilitators as trust brokers and catalysts**
Facilitators were central to the success of clusters. They connected farmers to funding schemes, organized events, and maintained momentum. In clusters where facilitation was weak or absent, motivation and cohesion declined. In contrast, strong facilitators helped farmers overcome institutional barriers and supported the emergence of collective goals.
- **Tangible identity change drives lasting behavioural change**
Interviewed farmers increasingly used terms such as "nature-friendly farming" and "responsibility to future generations." In some cases, farmers who were initially sceptical of biodiversity initiatives began leading on conservation projects. These identity shifts were accompanied by concrete actions—tree planting, hedgerow restoration, agroforestry—undertaken without coercive policy measures.
- **Variation across contexts underscores need for local adaptation**
While the FC model worked across diverse contexts, local histories, environmental conditions, and social dynamics shaped its success. In the Netherlands, previous experience with farmer collectives smoothed adoption. In Scotland, cultural individualism required more effort to build trust. EU-level policy must therefore support locally adapted facilitation rather than a one-size-fits-all model.

Conclusion

Facilitated Farmer Clusters (FCs) foster peer learning, cooperation, and stronger social norms

Participation in FCs increases the legitimacy of agri-environmental schemes (AES)

Effective facilitation is essential for promoting social learning in FCs

Farmer Clusters foster deeper, longer-lasting **engagement with biodiversity** by changing how farmers see themselves and each other. The shift from isolated farm-level action to **socially embedded learning communities** enables more meaningful and resilient behavioural change. While identity is often overlooked in policy design, it is a powerful lever.

To scale this success, EU agri-environmental policy must move **beyond financial incentives** alone and support the **social infrastructure** – especially facilitation and peer learning – that drives change from within farming communities.

Policy Implications

- If farmers participate in facilitated clusters, they are more likely to adopt and sustain biodiversity-enhancing practices.
- If EU agri-environmental policy continues to overlook social learning and identity, behavioural change will remain fragmented and short-lived.
- If facilitation roles are professionalized and supported, they can become central nodes in the EU's biodiversity strategy.

References

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